

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D4.1 – UP2030 Implementation plan for the pilot cities 1

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

Contact Email: contact@up2030-he.eu

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Author(s)	Leon Kapetas (RCities), Lina Liakou (RCities), Nilofer Tajuddin (RCities)			
Reviewer(s)	Aurelija Matuleviciute (TSPA) Alessandra Sammartino (TSPA), Trinidad Fernandez (Fraunhofer), Constanza Vera (Fraunhofer), Catalina Diaz (USTUTT)			
Abstract	Compiles the plans that cities have created for the implementation of UP2030 activities in the first year of the project. Gives an overview of the steps that will guide the process and the key insights that were identified from each city’s work planning. Ways of working with cities and liaisons, other WPs and project partners and key milestones guiding the project have also been compiled.			

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Executive summary

UP2030's objective is to leverage innovation, holistic urban planning, and design approaches to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets in an inclusive manner with their stakeholders, thereby building capacity to develop systemic approaches to achieving climate goals through their day-to-day activities.

The 'Pilot Implementation Plan' is the first step to define the processes that cities will follow to operationalise the UP2030 approach in their respective contexts. To this end, this first version of the Pilot Implementation Plan consists of (i) a 'City Storyline' as a narrative tool to streamline the scope of each pilot and (ii) a 'Workplan' which is a planning tool to understand common project milestones, city specific factors and timelines that are important for UP2030 implementation on a local level. This Pilot Implementation Plan has been and will continue to be an essential foundation to better coordinate exchanges and support for the cities from other WPs in UP2030, as well as identify key insights on opportunities, similarities, and potential risks to be mitigated in the cities.

Cities are identifying avenues to merge efforts to not double up engagement activities. The Pilot Implementation Plan development process has also allowed a critical reflection on our methodology to go beyond matching cities with solutions, but rather creating a co-creation process that allows cities to experiment and receive tailor-made support from the research and innovation partners. This has also led to the identification of "front-runner" cities that, based on their unique focus in UP2030, can serve as learning opportunities for all other city pilots. For instance, in the case of Granollers, the design and implementation of its engagement workshops will be replicated across the other cities.

Few cities have flagged that internal process and events (such as local elections) will impact the timing of organization of workshops and other engagement activities. Some cities are also in the process of building internal capacity through the hiring of new staff. In all cases, cities understand that engaging stakeholders, both internal and external, must be done in an inclusive manner and, hence, cities are also paying attention to engaging all the relevant ones in a strategic manner. This impacts the timeline and the approach since key stakeholders also need time to be engaged and participate in the process. Additionally, cities are also identifying milestones and opportunities for alignment with other ongoing work in the city to ensure sustainability and efficiency. This is also significant in the cities which are among the 112 selected by the European Commission's "Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities".

Through this report, the project has, very early on, set up initial plans for cities to implement and iterate over the first year of the project. It serves as a living document which will be reviewed at the end of the first year and updated with the lessons learned (D.4.2., M12). Furthermore, this report is also helpful as a reference document for coordination with other projects within the Cluster of Urban Planning and Design of the Mission, and specifically for the inception plan.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AQUATEC	AQUATEC Proyectos Para El Sector Del Agua Sa
D	Deliverable
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
GUNAM	ODTU – GUNAM - Centre for Solar Energy Research and Applications
ICA	I-Catalist
LAA	Learning Action Alliances
LINKS	Fondazione LINKS - Leading Innovation & Knowledge for Society
LNEC	Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil
MDAT	Major Development Agency Thessaloniki
METU	Middle East Technical University
MfC	Mapping for Change
RCities	Resilient Cities Network
TUD	Technische Universiteit Delft
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
UPV	Valencia Polytechnic University
VM	Vesela Motika
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The Deliverable 4.1 ‘UP2030 Pilot Implementation Plan for Pilot Cities 1’, compiles the plan of activities that cities will implement within UP2030 in the first year of the project. This report consists of the overall methodology that will guide the project, the process that cities undertook to plan out their actions, and the key insights that were identified as a result. It also provides more insights into how cities are working together with City Liaisons (see Section 2.2.1) and other partners from the various WPs in UP2030. Additionally, this report also maps out common milestones, opportunities for further collaboration and expected next steps.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 - Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ Section 2 – Methodology: Objectives, process of working and overview of Pilot Implementation Planning process
- ❖ Section 3 – Key Insights from Pilot Implementation Plan: Observations from analysis of cities’ storylines and workplans
- ❖ Section 4 – Conclusion and next steps: Key takeaways and expected next iteration of this report

2 Methodology

2.1 Objectives

By leveraging innovative and holistic urban planning and design approaches, UP2030's overall objective is to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets, helping city stakeholders and local authorities put neutrality and resilience on the map of their communities in day-to-day actions and strategic decisions. The objectives will be achieved by developing and applying an innovative methodology that cities can adopt to meaningfully engage with the Mission (5UP-approach). This methodology comprises the backbone of UP2030 by (i) updating cities' vision through consistent policy development, (ii) upskilling in state-of-the-art approaches, (iii) prototyping upgrades, and ultimately (iv) upscaling city-wide neutrality actions. This will be achieved through the co-development and implementation of science-based – yet practical - tools, and methods which will guide cities to deliver across the values of equity, resilience, neutrality, and sustainability within specific pilot projects in their cities.

In order to operationalize this 5-UP approach and to set up a coordination flow of actions in the cities, each city developed a 'Pilot Implementation Plan' that consists of a City Story Line and a Workplan as their first step. The implementation plan will help identify the specific activities and timeframes for the development of the pilots, while also providing the necessary background and baseline information that is needed to ensure that all partners across the project are aware of. The implementation plans reflect both the common activities that are part of the project's overarching implementation methodology and the specific steps each city needs to take based on their stakeholders' timelines and capabilities.

2.2 Working together with Cities and Liaisons

The UP2030 consortium comprises of **8 EU cities** (Budapest, Granollers, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, Zagreb; including MDAT, E-Nova as the operational arms of Thessaloniki & Lisbon respectively), **1 associated country city** (Istanbul) and **1 transitional arrangement city** (Belfast).

Rio de Janeiro also participates in the project as an "observer city". Considering that Rio de Janeiro does not receive financial resources from UP2030, a lighter engagement process has been agreed where the city focuses on implementation and looks to capitalise on the technical expertise available in the project. Hence, this city has not followed the process laid out in sections 2.2.2 and 2.3 and will not prepare the same documentation.

2.2.1 Coordination between Cities and City Liaisons

In UP2030, each pilot's activities are led by the city team in collaboration with its City Liaison. The liaisons are Research and Innovation partners of the project from the same country as the pilot city, for logistical and language reasons, who help the cities engage more efficiently and deeper with the project through direct support. The liaison is the main point of contact of the project with the cities. They manage the process with the city and together review information and formulate implementation and action plans. The liaison coordinates with WP4 partners to provide updates and present needs that will be communicated to the other WPs. See Table 1 for list of partners working with the cities as City Liaisons.

Table 1: Partners working together with cities as City Liaisons

City Name	City Liaison
Belfast	MfC
Budapest	GGGI
Granollers	AQUATEC
Istanbul	GUNAM/ METU
Granollers	LNEC
Milan	LINKS
Muenster	Fraunhofer
Rio de Janeiro	TUD
Rotterdam	RCities
Thessaloniki	MDAT
Zagreb	VM

2.2.2 Implementation methodology

All cities follow a common implementation process that consist of phases organized as per the Implementation methodology for the Learning Action Alliances (LAAs) (see Milestone 4 of the project in Figure 4). These LAAs are living labs consisting of diverse stakeholders from each city who together go through the various steps of the project as defined in the Implementation methodology for LAAs in the Grant Agreement (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Implementation methodology at the pilot environments run through participation activities (adaptation of Design Thinking steps)¹

¹ IDEOU – What is design thinking?

- **Step 1: Analysis:** “empathize”² to create each pilot case profile. This step supports the identification of needs, baseline conditions, and barriers for the city and its stakeholders.
- **Step 2: Vision:** ideate and think in systems, also tap into the creative abilities of participants that typically get overlooked to generate the vision through workshops. Link the vision to metrics and identify high-impact factor actions. Preparation of the roadmap implementation is needed to move to Step 3.
- **Step 3: Action:** Implement roadmaps to prototype pilot solutions, including designs of physical interventions, digital tools, products, and new policies.
- **Step 4: Evaluate:** Explore success through validation of metrics and based on new knowledge, examine opportunities for further upscale.

Each step consists of a key **workshop** that will be planned to engage stakeholders, gather feedback, and foster innovation. Further activities such as desk research, surveys, and consultations may be planned as per the city’s needs. The purpose of these activities is to meaningfully engage stakeholders and communities in the planning and design of the pilot with the objective of contributing to the city’s vision (to be developed within T2.4) on becoming climate neutral. The objective of this process is to embed new urban design tools and methods in everyday practice, ensuring the neutrality vision is an equitable one that engages the unusual suspects and ensuring that this way of working is mainstreamed in policy and governance of the city.

2.3 Pilot Implementation Plan

For the process of setting up the Pilot Implementation Plan, RCities developed templates to capture each city’s objective and expected outcomes through the UP2030 project, and the projected activities to be carried out in order to achieve them. The ‘Pilot Implementation Plan’ hence consists of these two documents that each city has developed using the templates, namely, the ‘City Storyline’ and ‘Work Plan’.

2.3.1 City Storyline

The City Storyline is a living document that has been created as a ‘narrative building tool’ for cities to develop their pilot case scope further. The city storyline will be periodically updated and used as a database for other WPs to understand the framework, needs, and context specific characteristics of the pilot, in order to better customise the approaches, tools, and methods developed throughout the project. As a result, the story lines give and receive feedback from Task 2.3 (in Q1-Q2 of the project) and Task T2.4 (in Q3-Q4 of the project). Figure 2 shows an example of Rotterdam’s storyline.

RCities developed a template with guiding questions exploring the following aspects:

- Historic influences on the pilot site.
- Spatial characteristics of the neighbourhood with reflections on UP2030 urban design approaches of compact, connected and net-zero city.
- Social characteristics of the neighbourhood with reflection on UP2030 principles of participation, social, and spatial justice.
- Challenges and opportunities for exploration

² “Empathise” looks into understanding people/agents deeper (understand the way they do things and why, their physical and emotional needs, how they think about the world, and what is meaningful to them). This can refer to city employees through to specific citizen groups that interventions will target.

- Current policies and programs taken by the city in the pilot site.
- Preliminary assessment of objectives, needs, and aspirations through the UP2030 project.
- Preliminary understanding of important stakeholders in the neighbourhood and city to be engaged.

Each city has opted to present the above information in a semi-structured manner that fits its narrative and the current stage of work. Hence, differentiations among story lines can be expected.

The first versions of the city storylines were developed in March 2023 (M3) of the project and will continue to be updated during the various stages of the project. A final storyline will be published at the end of the first year (M12). Cities expressed that the storyline has been useful to compile their approach and the factors influencing it and as a tool to streamline the focus on UP2030 activities in their context.

Figure 2 - Example city storyline using the case of Rotterdam BoTu neighbourhood

2.3.2 Work Plans

With the broader goals set through the city storyline, a Workplan template was created to capture the implementation of each city’s UP2030 activities (Figure 3). The template considers, the general activities that are common across all cities, and is further developed to include city specific activities and milestones that are important for the project.

With respect to the timelines that appear in the template, they are consistent with those that were presented in the Grant Agreement; nonetheless, the reality in the cities and the project evolution might mean that certain phases are rolled out earlier or later. For instance, initiating the Visioning phase requires completing the Needs Assessment. These variations in timeline are a direct result of the influencing factors identified to have an impact on the cities’ activities. The influences have been captured in Section 3. Each pilot will update its progress separately in their customised Work Plans.

First versions of the Work Plan were created by cities in March 2023 (M3) of the project and will be finalised in M12. Key insights from the first version have been shared in Section 3.

Work Plan for Pilot Activities				Month	Feb/23	Mar/23	Apr/23	May/23	Jun/23	Jul/23	Aug/23	Sep/23	Oct/23	Nov/23	Dec/23
				Weeks	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4	
Stage	Detailed steps to be taken	Partner responsible	Comments												
Create city storyline and plan of action	Create a story of the pilot focusing on the challenges and initial needs identified	City and Liaison													
	Define work plan (this excel document)	City and Liaison													
	D.4.1.UP2030 implementation plan for the pilot cities (part 1)	R-Cities	R-Cities will use this excel sheet per pilot to define this deliverable												
	D.4.2.UP2030 implementation plan for the pilot cities (Part 2)	R-Cities													
Stakeholder Mapping for LAA Definition	Map stakeholders that need to be a part of the LAA and contact														
	Sign LAA consent form														
Needs Assessment	Project Milestone - M4. All Cities have set up their LAAs														
	Preliminary identification of needs based on City storyline														
	Preliminary assessment of the SUPs for each pilot		Task.2.1. will provide feedback and input (D.2.1. The SUP approach and its contextualisation in the project cities June 2023)												
	Further definition of needs in alignment with SUPs														
	Project Milestone - M5. Cities run first workshop on needs/analysis		Task.2.3. will provide tools for this workshop (D2.4 – An interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality - August 2023)												
Visioning	Processing of needs & barriers analysed in workshop														
	Preliminary matching of tools to needs														
	Further contextualisation of city vision, pilot vision and SUPs		Task.2.4. will provide input on this (D2.5 – Report on vision co-design methodology report and its application for pilot shared visions - Dec 2023)												
	Creation of roadmap														
Activity 5	Project Milestone - M6. Cities run second workshop on vision														
	Project Milestone - M7. Cities establish their User stories														

Figure 3 - Template prepared for city Work Planning

2.3.3 Milestones and timelines for UP2030 Pilot cities

All Cities follow common activities over the course of the UP2030 timeline. The 4 key workshops with the city’s LAAs are the highlights in this timeline (Figure 4). The first workshop focuses on the needs/analysis stage, the second is on visioning, the third is on action and the fourth is on upscaling. As mentioned in section 2.2.2, these milestones are based on the implementation methodology of the project.

Figure 4 - Timeline of milestones and deliverables planned

2.4 Opportunities for alignments with other Work Packages

The implementation of activities in the pilots is achieved through the close collaboration and alignment with various tasks spread across the UP2030 project WPs, namely:

- WP2 – UP-DATING (led by UIC)– Understanding cities’ and stakeholders’ needs for upgrading, and co-designing visions of urban transformations.

- WP3 – UP-SKILLING (led by TUD) - Empowering the city's stakeholder ecosystem to codevelop urban planning and design enabled transformation pathways.
- WP4 – UP-GRADING (led by RCities) - Piloting and demonstrating. (WP responsible for this document)
- WP5 – UP-SCALING (led by ICLEI) - Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making.

Task T2.1, led by the project coordinator, Fraunhofer, is responsible for aligning expectations and activities across WPs. T2.1 is also critical for building shared scientific and process understanding across the project partners. This applies also for the activities specific to T4.1. In particular, for the delivery of the Analysis workshops in each pilot city, the different WPs work in an integrated manner as described below. This alignment process is visualised in Figure 5. Note that for the following three workshops, a new alignment process will be elaborated.

1. WP4 through Task 4.1 led by RCities) provides the base information on each pilot's case profile through the city storyline and Work Plan.
2. WP4 through Task 4.2 led by ICA provides the methodology for mapping stakeholders that need to be engaged through the LAA and provides the guidelines on setting up the LAAs in each city.
3. The City Liaison and City lead the organization of the workshops in their city.
4. WP2 through Task 2.3 led by MfC develops the stakeholder engagement methods that the workshops will follow at each stage. These methods will be customised per city by the Liaison.
5. WP2 through Task 2.2 led by UIC, develops the State-of-the-Art concepts and approaches in planning and design according to the SUP approach to be applied in the pilot cities.
6. WP3 provides tools and methods to be tested as necessary.

Figure 5 - Alignment between WPs for the design and delivery of the Analysis workshop in Pilot Cities

To ensure that the methodologies developed are responsive to the needs and capabilities of the cities, certain tools and approaches will be tested in specific pilot cases before being streamlined across all cities. For instance:

- The city of Granollers will be the first city to deliver a workshop on the 29th of March 2023. UP2030 partners ICA, MfC, UIC and RCities together with the City Liaison and City are developing a methodology for this workshop that will be tested in Granollers. Lessons learned will be integrated into the methodology post implementation. This updated methodology will then be applied to other pilot cities workshops.
- In the city of Milan, the objective of the UP2030 activities is to develop a Monitoring and Evaluation Framework that will compile metrics and KPIs to monitor the city’s railyard redevelopment. Given its focus on KPIs as an output, UPV, which is leading Task 4.3 on the development of KPIs for the whole project, will work closely with the city of Milan to analyse KPIs that can directly benefit the output of Milan in the UP2030 project while supporting the overall M&E approach of the project.

3 Key Insights from the Pilot Implementation Plans

Through the process of developing the City Storyline and Workplans and their analysis, common threads among cities have been identified, both in terms of risks that might impact the timely implementation of the project and in terms of opportunities that can further enhance the outcomes of the project. Specifically:

- **Political changes** such as local or national elections in Spain (May 2023), Thessaloniki (May and October 2023), Istanbul (May 2023) might lead to a deviation from the projects' timeline. Partners and cities are managing this risk by proactively identifying the activities that might be impacted and use the specific moments as opportunities to further accelerate other types of activities (i.e. Data analysis or desk research). As an example: Granollers accelerated the timeline for their first workshop to make sure it took place before any pre-election restrictions.
- Some cities (i.e. Milan or Thessaloniki) are still in the **process of finalizing their recruitments** for the people that will manage the project internally. This by consequence means that the city has limited capacity to organize big public workshops. To mitigate this, liaison partners are working more proactively in supporting these cities and prioritizing activities and workshops that do not require a heavy lift from a logistics perspective.
- **Cities need time to engage their internal stakeholders and communicate** about the objectives and purpose of the UP2030 project before being able to reach out and include more external partners and local communities. This is also why the first workshop of the city is usually dedicated to the internal stakeholders trying to identify the roles, responsibilities, and needs of the various departments and city officers in relation to the specific pilots. The workshops that are identified in the overarching methodology of the project should be considered as the start of the engagement process for each phase that includes several other activities to be defined in alignment with WP2 and more specifically taking in consideration the outcomes from T2.2 and T2.3, going from public surveys to focus groups and 1:1 interviews.
- In all cases, **cities have identified additional steps to be taken beyond** UP2030 planned activities (see milestones mapped in Figure 4). Through this process of developing the specific workplans we were able to identify opportunities from activities that the cities are already planning in doing that can align with the objectives and steps of the project. These include, aligning the first workshop (Milestone 5, April M4) with the existing activities under the Climate City Contract development process in Lisbon and Istanbul or a public conference in Rotterdam that will create the opportunity to further engage with a diverse group of citizens and communities that would be difficult to reach out otherwise. For the pilot cities that are also part of the 112 selected for the Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart cities, it is essential to coordinate efforts on a city level since the pilot activities can contribute to the Climate City Contracts.
- By developing the City Storylines, the city together with the liaison had the **opportunity to further mature the scope** and narrative of the pilot project that is critical in ensuring that all activities align with the scope and contribute to the overall objectives identified. In particular, the implementation planning process so far has offered a first opportunity to cities to explore how their pilots can be shaped to make their districts better connected, more compact and carbon-efficient, i.e., meet the urban planning and design objectives of the project. This, by consequence, will lead to activities that create real value to the city and the local communities within.
- The LAAs play an important role in steering the project in the pilot cities, and hence the cities want to **ensure that the process and selection of stakeholders is as inclusive as possible**. To this end,

cities have mapped their stakeholders and will be engaging with them on a one-to-one basis and/or through smaller working groups. Cities need more time to do this extensive engagement with the stakeholders. In some cases, the first workshop plays an essential step as well. Hence, the LAAs will be formalized in June 2023 (M6). As of M3 of the project, cities have provided an initial assessment of the expected participants of their LAAs. In the meantime, cities continue to finalize the design and structure of these LAAs for their project contexts.

- Taking a socio-technical transition approach means that the ambition of **the UP2030 project goes beyond matching specific technical solutions to specific cities**. Rather, a series of tools and methods will need to be combined and adapted to address specific city needs, as these are extracted during the ongoing engagement process. These combinations of tailored methods and tools will form part of implementation roadmaps developed in the first year of the project and will be reflected in the future development of the implementation plans. Lastly, the socio-technical transition approach means that the implementation plan will address capacity gaps and stakeholder acceptance risks in the pilot cities.
- During the process, it was recognized that each city, through its approach and focus, can also serve as lessons for the other cities involved in UP2030. Hence, several cities are front-runners for specific processes within UP2030. For instance:
 - Granollers is the first city to kick-off its engagement workshops and hence this will be used as a testing ground for methodologies that can be used to engage the stakeholders.
 - Lisbon's focus is on creating a catalogue of solutions based on measuring the impact created on the city's climate neutrality goals. Through its activities, it can test out the methodology of selection of tools and the innovation that can be achieved by applying these tools in a curated process. Similarly, through its Healthy Streets Call for Action, Budapest creates a testing ground for the parameters for implementation of solutions on the ground.
 - Milan's focus is to create a Monitoring and Evaluation Framework for the pilot site's Masterplan implementation. They are hence a frontrunner in the development of KPIs and measurement criteria that can be transferred as lessons to other cities.
 - Rotterdam leads the process of creating policy recommendation for upscaling through the creation of a blueprint that critically analyses and repositions its ongoing programs.
 - As mentioned in section 2.2, Rio de Janeiro follows a lighter engagement process because it does not receive any financial resources from UP2030. Rio de Janeiro's focus is specifically on how their funding received by the Interamerican Bank of Development ensures that it meets the adaptation and climate neutrality objectives set out. In this sense, this city plays a role as a front-runner in aligning with financing instruments.
 - Istanbul leads the process of leveraging digital solutions to increase data informed urban planning.

4 Conclusion and next steps

Through the ‘Pilot Implementation Plan’ consisting of the City Storyline and Workplan, cities have developed a more in-depth understanding of the scope of the UP2030 approach and its implementation in their contexts. This plan also provides contextual information for project partners to deliver customized input and support to the cities. In addition to the common project milestones, the Pilot Implementation Plan uncovers the actions that need to be taken in the cities to achieve the objectives of the project, the risks of implementation and the strategies to mitigate the risks.

Several common factors such as local elections, hiring of project staff and limitations on available time to meaningfully engage local stakeholders for setting up the LAAs have been identified. Cities are also aligning with other activities and milestones that can support the UP2030 timeline in their local settings. For instance, alignment with the Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities is also considered.

A key takeaway has been identifying front-runner cities that can test certain approaches and then transfer the lessons to other pilots, i.e., use an agile implementation approach with short learning cycles. This also reinforces the matching making and collective learning approach of UP2030.

This report is a first step to plan the first year of the project implementation in each of the pilot cities. It is a living document that will be continuously updated and a revised version will be developed at the end of December 2023 (M12). Current versions of the Pilot Implementation Plan documents are not published along with this report at this stage.

Additionally, this report provides insight to the other Cluster projects with the Urban Design and Planning Call under the Cities Mission.